

NOTES

Crystal Data on ZnTaCuO₄

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Manuscript received 8 August 1977, revised 15 February 1978,

accepted 23 March 1978

A survey of recent literature on the ternary oxides of the chemical formula XYZO₄ showed that the compound ZnTaCuO₄ has not been synthesized. Earlier we reported¹ the crystal structure of ZnNbCuO₄ which is found to have a face-centered orthorhombic structure. The compound reported here

ther the appropriate oxides² of A. R grade in proper molar ratio. The mixture was heated in air at 950° for 70 hours. The X-ray diffraction pattern recorded on a Debye-Scherrer camera (114.6 mm diameter) using filtered copper radiation indicated the presence of a single phase. The three principal diffraction lines as given in ASTM data of the reacting oxides were absent in the pattern. The crystallographic results are given in Table 1. All the observed reflections are indexed on the basis of orthorhombic unit cell having $a=8.58 \pm 0.002\text{A}$, $b=8.86 \pm 0.002\text{A}$ and $c=9.54 \pm 0.002\text{A}$. It is evident from the observed reflections that the Bravais lattice is primitive. This clearly shows that the crystal structure of ZnTaCuO₄ is different from that of ZnNbCuO₄ and hence Ta⁵⁺ ions do not substitute Nb⁵⁺ ions in the crystal structure.

TABLE—1

d				ZnTaCuO ₄ Zinc-Tantalum-Copper Oxide.						
I/I ₀	2.597	3.12	1.764	4.766	d in A	I/I ₀	h k l	d in A	I/I ₀	h k l
Rad :	=1.54 A									
Filter :	Nickel									
Dia :	11.46 cm	D. S. Camera								
Int :	Visual									
Sys :	Orthorhombic	SG :—								
	a ₀	b ₀	c ₀							
	8.58	8.86	9.54							
					4.77	15	0 0 2	1.34	5	2 6 2
					4.33	15	2 0 0	1.29	10	6 3 0
					3.90	15	2 0 1			4 4 4
					3.74	20	1 1 2	1.26	20	5 1 5
					3.56	10	2 1 1	1.24	5	1 7 1
					3.23	10	0 2 2	1.20	5	7 1 1
					3.12	70	2 2 0	1.18	10	7 2 0
					2.97	20	0 3 0			6 2 4
							1 0 3	1.16	25	3 7 0
					2.68	35	1 3 1	1.14	5	7 2 2
					2.60	100	2 2 2	1.12	10	2 4 7
					2.50	40	0 3 2	1.09	20	3 7 3
					2.38	40	0 0 4	1.06	<5	8 1 1
					2.17	45	4 0 0	1.02	<5	2 4 8
					2.12	50	3 0 3	1.00	<5	0 8 4
					1.97	5	2 4 0	0.996	10	1 6 7
					1.94	10	4 2 0	0.951	5	7 2 6
					1.76	60	0 2 5	0.928	10	0 6 8
					1.73	30	3 3 3	0.906	5	0 8 6
					1.67	20	5 1 1	0.877	15	0 9 5
					1.65	30	3 4 2	0.861	5	0 6 9
					1.61	15	0 4 4	0.846	10	6 4 8
					1.55	30	4 4 0	0.829	5	9 5 2
					1.48	50	0 6 0	0.819	10	6 3 9
					1.43	15	5 0 0	0.807	5	1 8 8
					1.41	50	0 6 2	0.788	20	8 2 8
					1.37	10	6 0 2	0.782	10	9 0 7
								0.779	10	11 0 0
								0.776	5	6 7 7

may be regarded as a substitution of Ta⁵⁺ ions for Nb⁵⁺ ions in ZnNbCuO₄, since Nb⁵⁺ and Ta⁵⁺ ions have the same oxidation number and comparable ionic radii³ (Ta⁵⁺=0.71 and Nb⁵⁺=0.70A).

The compound has been prepared for the first time. It was prepared by intimately mixing toge-

References

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